

1 **Exploring short-term leaf-litter decomposition dynamics in a**
2 **Mediterranean ecosystem: dependence on litter type and site conditions.**

3
4 **Corresponding Author:**

5 Miss María Almagro, mbonmati@cebas.csic.es

6 **Corresponding Author's Institution:**

7 Departamento de Conservación de Suelos y Aguas, Centro de Edafología y Biología Aplicada
8 del Segura- Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CEBAS-CSIC)

9 Campus Universitario de Espinardo 30100, Murcia (Spain)

10 Tel: +34 968 396 200; Fax: (+34) 968 396 213

11 **Order of Authors:**

12 María Almagro, María Martínez-Mena.

13 **Coauthor's Institution:**

14 Departamento de Conservación de Suelos y Aguas, Centro de Edafología y Biología Aplicada
15 del Segura- Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CEBAS-CSIC) Campus

16 Universitario de Espinardo 30100, Murcia (Spain)

17 Tel: +34 968 396 200; Fax: (+34) 968 396 213

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28 **Abstract**

29 **Aims** Plant litter decomposition plays an important role in the storage of soil organic
30 matter in terrestrial ecosystems. Conversion of native vegetation to agricultural lands and
31 subsequent land abandonment can lead to shifts in canopy structure, and consequently
32 influence decomposition dynamics by alterations in soil temperature and moisture conditions,
33 solar radiation exposure, and soil erosion patterns. This study was conducted to assess which
34 parameters were more closely related to short-term decomposition dynamics of two
35 predominant Mediterranean leaf litter types.

36 **Methods** Using the litterbag technique, we incubated leaf litter of *Pinus halepensis* and
37 *Rosmarinus officinalis* in two Mediterranean land-uses with different degree of vegetation
38 cover (open forest, abandoned agricultural field).

39 **Results** Fresh local litter lost between 20 and 55% of its initial mass throughout the 20-
40 month incubation period. Rosemary litter decomposed faster than pine litter, showing net N
41 immobilization in the early stages of decomposition, in contrast to the net N release exhibited
42 by pine litter. Parameters related to litter quality (N content or C:N) or land-use/site
43 conditions (ash content, an index of soil deposition on litter) were found to explain the cross-
44 site variability in mass loss rates for rosemary and Aleppo pine litter, respectively.

45 **Conclusions** The results from this study suggest that decomposition drivers may differ
46 depending on litter type in this Mediterranean ecosystem. While rosemary litter was degraded
47 mainly by microbial activity, decomposition of pine litter was likely driven primarily by
48 abiotic processes like soil erosion.

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51 **Key words:** Carbon cycle; Litter decomposition; Mediterranean ecosystem; N
52 immobilization; Soil erosion; Vegetation structure.

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54

55 INTRODUCTION

56 Plant litter decomposition is a key component in the terrestrial ecosystem carbon (C) and
57 nitrogen (N) cycles, and it provides the primary source of nutrients for plants, and of both
58 nutrients and energy for soil microorganisms (Currie 2003). As a result of ongoing global
59 climate change, and the increasingly acknowledged importance of the roles of litter and soil
60 organic matter as potential C sinks, much effort is being devoted to improving our
61 understanding of the mechanisms driving litter decomposition dynamics and subsequent soil
62 C storage.

63 Understanding the factors that control short-term litter decomposition dynamics is
64 particularly important in heterogeneous water-limited ecosystems, because of the small
65 amount of soil organic matter and low availability of mineral nutrients (Carreira et al. 1996;
66 Rashid and Ryan 2004) compared with other ecosystems. Additionally, the high
67 mineralization rates (Martínez-Mena et al. 2002), and the episodic nature of precipitation
68 events (Austin et al. 2004; Huxman et al. 2004) and associated soil water erosion processes
69 (Martínez-Mena et al. 2001) might constrain the C sequestration potential of these
70 ecosystems, making them highly susceptible to global change and prone to degradation.

71 Extensive research has focused on predicting litter decay rates based on climate, litter
72 quality and soil biotic interactions (Aerts 1997; Berg et al. 1993, 2010; Coûteaux et al. 1995;
73 Kurz-Besson et al. 2006). However, models from mesic ecosystems are unsuited to water-
74 limited ecosystems (Collins et al. 2008; Parton et al. 2007; Whitford et al. 1981). The
75 differences observed regarding decomposition drivers between mesic and dry ecosystems may
76 be partly explained by the patchy distribution of vegetation and resources in the latter. Unlike
77 mesic ecosystems where vegetation cover is continuous and decomposition processes are
78 predominantly biological (Moorhead and Sinsabaugh 2006), plant cover patterns in water-
79 limited ecosystems may influence decomposition rates through physicochemical processes
80 such as photodegradation (Austin and Vivanco 2006; Dirks et al. 2010), fragmentation by

81 raindrop splash (Whitford 2002), or soil erosion and runoff (Throop and Archer 2007; Berhe
82 2011), even in periods in which microbial activity is constrained.

83 The present study was undertaken as part of a project aimed at quantifying C pools and
84 fluxes (outputs and inputs), and assessing the factors controlling the main C fluxes within
85 different representative Mediterranean land-use types. In a previous study (Almagro et al.
86 2010), we estimated annual litter accumulation rates based on the annual litterfall inputs and
87 decay rates of the predominant litter types within each land-use/site. Interestingly, we
88 detected that the effect of land-use/site on decay rates differed between litter types. From
89 those results, a new research question arose concerning the factors controlling the
90 decomposition dynamics of two predominant Mediterranean leaf litter types (*Pinus halepensis*
91 Miller and *Rosmarinus officinalis* L). More specifically, the objectives of the current study
92 were: (1) to compare the mass loss rates and changes in nitrogen content of these two
93 predominant litter types and (2) to assess whether the parameters most closely related to
94 short-term decomposition dynamics differ between litter types.

95 Recent studies in other water-limited ecosystems addressing the roles of abiotic and biotic
96 factors in the litter decomposition process have highlighted that species with low-quality litter
97 are prone to greater mass loss by abiotic mechanisms (Austin and Ballaré 2010; Brandt et al.
98 2007; Day et al. 2007; Martínez-Yrizar et al. 2007; Uselman et al. 2011). Aleppo pine litter
99 has higher concentrations of lignin, suberin, resins, fats and waxes than rosemary litter (Berg
100 et al. 2010; Boddi et al. 2002; Kaloustian et al. 2000; Traversa et al. 2011; Vokou and Liotiri
101 1999), thus making the former more chemically recalcitrant and potentially resistant to
102 biodegradation (Minderman 1968; Rovira and Vallejo 2002). Thus, we hypothesized that
103 decomposition of rosemary litter (more labile and nutrient-rich) would be more closely related
104 to biotic factors such as microbial processes, while decomposition of Aleppo pine litter (more
105 recalcitrant and nutrient-poor) would be predominantly linked to abiotic processes.

106

107 MATERIALS AND METHODS

108 *Study area*

109 The study area was located in Cehegín in the northwest of the province of Murcia in S.E.
110 Spain. The climate is dry mesomediterranean with an average annual precipitation of 370
111 mm, which occurs mostly in autumn and spring. The mean annual temperature is relatively
112 high, 15.5 °C, and mean potential evapotranspiration (calculated by the Thornthwaite method;
113 Thornthwaite 1948) is 800 mm yr⁻¹, so the mean annual water deficit is 430 mm. July and
114 August are the driest months. Two sites were selected to carry out the study: 1) a circa 150-yr-
115 old mixed Aleppo pine-kermes oak open forest, and 2) an abandoned agricultural field, which
116 was cultivated with cereal for several years until abandonment in 1980, when establishment of
117 typical Mediterranean vegetation started. Both sites are covered with a typical Mediterranean
118 shrubland (*Rosmarinus officinalis* L., *Quercus coccifera* L., and *Juniperus oxycedrus* L.) with
119 scattered Aleppo pines (*Pinus halepensis* Miller). Although both sites show the same
120 dominant plant species, the open forest presents greater plant cover and aboveground biomass
121 than the abandoned agricultural field site (see Table 1a), thus resulting in a more developed
122 vegetation structure in the former. The soils in the study area, with a loamy texture, derived
123 from limestone colluvia (open forest) and Triassic marl colluvia (abandoned agricultural field),
124 are classified as Petric calcisol (open forest) and Calcaric regosol (abandoned agricultural
125 field), according to soil taxonomy (FAO 2006). The two sites are located on a glaxis hillslope
126 with a mean height of 640 m a.s.l., and a mean slope of 10-12%, good drainage and a high
127 percentage of surface stones.

128 *Precipitation, soil temperature and water content*

129 Precipitation depth, intensity and duration of each rainfall event were obtained from a
130 recording rain gauge installed in the experimental area. Soil temperature at 2 cm depth was
131 measured hourly using temperature probes connected to data-loggers (Hobbo, Onset
132 Computer Corporation, Bourne, MA, USA). Each land-use type had at least three temperature
133 probes. Soil volumetric water content (SWC) in the 0-10 cm depth interval was measured

134 every two weeks at different locations within each land-use using a time domain
135 reflectometry device (TDR).

136 *Canopy structure characterization*

137 The above mentioned study sites were divided into the following two microsites: patches
138 covered by *Pinus halepensis*, and open intershrub patches which were sparsely covered with
139 *Rosmarinus officinalis* shrubs. Replicate (n=4) plots (5 x 5 m) representative of each microsite
140 were established within each land-use type, and every shrub and tree stem basal diameter was
141 measured at the end of the growing season (2007) in order to estimate aboveground biomass
142 from species-specific allometric relationships (Baeza et al. 2006, 2011; Barberá et al.
143 unpublished data). Mean vegetation cover (%), stem density and litter layer thickness were
144 also determined.

145 *Soil sampling and analysis*

146 Prior to litterbag deployment, soil within the above mentioned microsites was sampled. In
147 December 2006 and April 2007, one soil core (10 cm diameter, 15 cm depth) was extracted
148 within each *microsite x land-use* combination (n = 4). Each soil core was sealed in a plastic
149 bag and stored in a freezer (4 °C) until processed for microbial biomass estimates, and C and
150 N analyses. Soil samples were air-dried, and sieved through a 2 mm sieve. The soil C and N
151 content in the mineral soil (<2 mm) was measured with a N/C analyzer (Flash 1112 EA,
152 Thermo-Finnigan, Bremen, Germany). Microbial biomass C was determined by fumigation
153 with ethanol-free chloroform and extraction with K₂SO₄ according to the procedure described
154 by Vance et al. (1987). A calibration factor $K_{EC} = 0.38$ was used. All soil analysis were done
155 in triplicate.

156 *Litter collection, initial litter traits and litterbag construction*

157 In April 2007, fresh litter samples of two predominant Mediterranean litter types were
158 collected weekly from several plastic sheets spread on the soil under tree/shrub canopies in
159 both sites: *Pinus halepensis* needles, fine stems and fruits, and *Rosmarinus officinalis* leaves,
160 flowers and stems. Litter samples were air-dried at room temperature. Oven-dry weight was

161 determined for five samples per litter type after drying at 55 °C for 4 days. Samples were
162 ground and analysed for C and N content in an elemental analyzer (Flash 1112 EA, Thermo-
163 Finnigan, Bremen, Germany) in order to assess the initial litter C and N content. Subsamples
164 (0.2 g) were combusted in a muffle furnace at 500 °C for 5 h to determine initial ash content.
165 In addition, leaf-litter macro- (P, K, Mg, Ca and S) and micro-nutrients (Fe, Zn and Mn)
166 concentrations were measured by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry
167 (ICP-OES, Thermo Elemental Iris Intrepid II XDL, Franklin, MA, USA) after a microwave-
168 assisted digestion with HNO₃:H₂O₂ (4:1, v:v). Each litter type was thoroughly mixed before
169 placing 3.0 g (*Rosmarinus officinalis* litter type) or 5.0 g (*Pinus halepensis* litter type) of
170 leaves and fine stems (± 0.01 g) inside 10 x 10 cm litterbags constructed of fibreglass-nylon
171 mesh with 1.4 mm² openings. The initial concentration of litter in the litterbags (500 g m⁻² in
172 pine and 300 g m⁻² in rosemary) was equivalent to about two years of accumulated litter
173 inputs, which averaged 280 and 146 g m⁻² yr⁻¹ for Aleppo pine and rosemary, respectively, in
174 the study area (personal observation).

175 *Litterbag deployment*

176 Two fenced plots were installed next to two randomly selected Aleppo pine trees and two
177 others next to two randomly selected rosemary shrubs in the open forest and abandoned
178 agricultural field sites. We placed litterbags with their corresponding litter types on the soil
179 surface inside the above-mentioned fenced plots on 19 June 2007 and followed their mass loss
180 for 20 months. Prior to litterbag deployment, the litter layer in Aleppo pine plots at the open
181 forest site was removed in order to incubate litterbags under the same conditions as in the
182 Aleppo pine plots at abandoned agricultural field site, which lacked of litter layer. A total of
183 72 litterbags were placed (2 litter types x 2 microsites x 6 sampling dates x 3 replicates) in the
184 open forest and abandoned agricultural field sites. Each litterbag was carried inside an
185 individual envelope to quantify how much litter was lost from the bags during transport. We
186 collected 3 litterbags from each fenced plot (henceforth referred to as “location”) every three
187 or four months.

188 *Sample analyses and decomposition rate*

189 Any material not derived from litter (seedlings, stones, soil fauna or fungi) was removed
190 by hand before the litterbags were dried at 55° C and sieved to remove mineral soil. After
191 drying for 4 days at 55° C the litter of each litterbag was weighed to determine mass change.
192 The litterbag contents were ground, and subsamples from each litterbag were combusted in a
193 muffle furnace at 500° C for 5 h to determine the ash content. All data were analyzed on an
194 ash-free dry matter basis in order to exclude any mass gain resulting from mineral soil that
195 entered the bags. The effect of soil particles transported by soil water erosion on litter mass
196 loss rates was explored using the percentage of ash remaining, which has shown good
197 correlation with decay rates in a water-limited ecosystem (Throop and Archer 2007).
198 However, this is a very conservative estimate of soil infiltration/deposition into litterbags
199 because: 1) some soil was previously removed by sieving; and 2) the ash-content may have
200 increased slightly with consecutive mineralization of organic substances. Subsamples from
201 each litterbag were analyzed for C and N content on an elemental analyzer (Flash 1112 EA,
202 Thermo-Finnigan, Bremen, Germany).

203 Litter decomposition was assumed to be the proportional difference in ash-free dry mass
204 between the initial (0 month) and successive litterbag collection dates. The decomposition
205 constant (k , yr⁻¹) was determined for each *litter type* x *land-use* combination using a single
206 exponential decay model (Olson 1963):

$$207 \quad M_t = M_0 e^{-kt} \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

208 where M_t and M_0 are the ash-free dry mass of the litter at time t and time 0.

209 *Statistical analyses*

210 Hourly temperature data were condensed into daily means for each location. The effect of
211 site on topsoil temperature and moisture were analyzed using repeated measures ANOVA.
212 Soil properties were analyzed with a two-way ANOVA, in which site and microsite were
213 considered the main effects. A t-test was performed to compare the initial nutrient
214 concentrations for each litter type. Changes in litterbag mass, C content and N content

215 throughout the study were analyzed using a three-way ANOVA. Litter type, site and time
216 were considered the main effects. Decay constants were analyzed with a two-way ANOVA, in
217 which litter type and site were the main effects. Differences in soil input into litterbags
218 between sites were also analyzed with one-way ANOVA. Prior to analysis data were natural-
219 log or arcsine transformed to meet ANOVA assumptions. Linear regression analyses were
220 performed separately for each litter type to evaluate the relationships between litter mass loss
221 and temperature, water availability or rainfall characteristics across collection dates. In
222 addition, parameters related to litter quality (N content or C:N) or infiltration/deposition of
223 soil particles into litterbags by water erosion (ash content) were included into multiple linear
224 regression models, and the stepwise procedure was used in order to assess their influence on
225 mass loss patterns for each litter type and sampling period separately. All analyses were
226 performed using SPSS 15.0 (Chicago, IL, USA).

227

228 **RESULTS**

229 *Rainfall, soil temperature and water content*

230 During the 20-month study period, rainfall events ranged from 1 mm to 70 mm, and
231 precipitation followed the typical bimodal distribution with two rainy seasons, autumn and
232 spring, and a dry period in summer (Fig. 1a). Accumulated rainfall in autumn 2008 (243 mm)
233 was three-fold higher than that in autumn 2007 (70 mm), highlighting the high rainfall
234 variability between years characteristic of Mediterranean regions. The highest rainfall amount
235 and intensity recorded for a single rainfall event were 70 mm and 25 mm h⁻¹ (maximum
236 rainfall intensity in 30 minutes, I_{30max}) (Fig. 1a), which occurred in October 2008. As a result,
237 accumulated soil erosion in autumn 2008 was 13-fold higher than that in autumn 2007
238 (Martínez-Mena et al. 2011). Both soil temperature (from 5 to 30°C) and moisture content
239 (from 5 to 34%) varied markedly with season (Fig. 1b; 1c), and were inversely correlated with
240 each other throughout the study period ($r = -0.55$, $P < 0.01$). There were no significant

241 differences in soil temperature or water content between land-uses/sites throughout the 20-
242 month study period.

243 *Canopy, soil characteristics and initial litter traits*

244 Whereas *Rosmarinus officinalis* patches exhibited similar canopy structure parameters
245 across sites (50.2 ± 4.5 and $41.2 \pm 4.7\%$ plant cover, 226.7 ± 26 and 162.5 ± 6.5 g of
246 aboveground biomass per square metre for open forest and abandoned agricultural field sites,
247 respectively), *Pinus halepensis* patches in the open forest showed two main differences from
248 those in the abandoned agricultural field site. First, Aleppo pine patches exhibited about two-
249 fold higher plant cover and aboveground biomass in the open forest ($90 \pm 6.7\%$ and $990.5 \pm$
250 362.1 g m⁻², respectively) than in the abandoned agricultural field site ($44.5 \pm 6.0\%$ and 472.5
251 ± 152 g m⁻², respectively). Second, while there was a nearly continuous 4 cm thick litter layer
252 beneath the Aleppo pine canopies in the open forest site, the litter layer was negligible
253 beneath Aleppo pine canopies in the abandoned agricultural field site.

254 At the beginning of the decomposition experiment, soil under both Aleppo pine and
255 rosemary patches showed significantly higher organic C and total N contents in the open
256 forest than in the abandoned agricultural field site (Table 1b). Soil microbial biomass beneath
257 Aleppo pine canopies was significantly greater in the open forest than in the abandoned
258 agricultural field site. However, rosemary patches did not show significant differences in soil
259 microbial biomass between sites.

260 Analysis of leaf-litter nutrient concentrations (see Table 2) showed significantly lower
261 contents of some macro- (P, K, Mg, Ca and S) and micro-nutrients (Fe, Zn and Mn) in Aleppo
262 pine than in rosemary litter.

263 *Litter mass loss*

264 Litterbag mass for both sites and litter types decreased with time (Fig.2a), following a
265 single exponential decay model. However, different mass loss patterns were observed
266 between litter types. Whereas rosemary litter showed the greatest mass loss in the first eight
267 months of the experiment, Aleppo pine litter decomposed slowly and gradually until the last

268 stages of the decomposition experiment, when mass loss increased considerably (Fig.2a). For
269 all sampling periods, rosemary litter decomposed more rapidly than Aleppo pine litter across
270 sites ($t = - 8.38$; $P < 0.0001$). After 20 months, rosemary litterbags had significantly less
271 remaining mass than did Aleppo pine litterbags, regardless of land-use/site (pooled across
272 sites: rosemary = $44.77\% \pm 2.21\%$ (mean \pm SE), Aleppo pine = $70.25\% \pm 2.21\%$; $F = 132.18$;
273 $P < 0.0001$).

274 The influence of land-use/site on mass loss rates was not consistently statistically
275 significant throughout the decomposition experiment and differed between litter types. While
276 a site effect on mass loss rates was apparent for rosemary litter during the first stages of the
277 decomposition experiment, the mass loss rates of Aleppo pine litter did not differ between
278 land-uses/sites until the last stages of the decomposition experiment (Fig.2a), when most
279 high-intensity rainfall events and associated erosion process occurred in the experimental area
280 (Fig.1a; Martínez-Mena et al. 2011). At the end of the incubation period, the influence of
281 land-use/site on decay rates (k) was significant for both species (Fig. 3), although no
282 consistent patterns were observed between the two litter types. Rosemary litter decomposed
283 faster in the open forest than in the abandoned agricultural site ($t = - 2.25$; $P = 0.027$), while
284 decomposition rates of Aleppo pine litter were higher in the abandoned agricultural field site
285 than in the open forest site ($t = -2.33$; $P = 0.023$) (Fig. 3).

286 *Changes in C and N during decomposition*

287 Initial mean C percentage in rosemary litter was not significantly different from that in
288 pine litter ($P = 0.517$) (Table 2). For both species, C losses closely followed mass loss patterns,
289 leading to a strong linear relationship between remaining mass and remaining C, with no
290 significant site effects ($P = 0.352$) (Fig.4a).

291 The initial nitrogen percentage in rosemary litter did not differ from that in pine litter
292 ($P = 0.871$) (Table 2). For both species, N percentage peaked at the 17-month collection date
293 ($1.87\% \pm 0.04\%$ and $1.18\% \pm 0.04\%$ for rosemary and pine litter, respectively), and then
294 declined. However, before these peaks were reached, temporal patterns in N percentage

295 differed between litter types ($R^2 = 0.87$; $F = 562.234$; $P < 0.0001$). During the first stages of
296 decomposition rosemary litter showed net N immobilization, while pine litter showed net N
297 release until about 20% of the mass was lost (Fig.2b). Although higher peaks of net N
298 immobilization were observed in the open forest than in the abandoned agricultural field site
299 for both litter types, the influence of site on maximum net N immobilization was only
300 significant in the case of rosemary litter ($P < 0.05$).

301 Initial C:N ratios did not differ between litter types (Table 2). However, temporal trends
302 in C:N ratios differed between litter types, and subsequently the C:N ratios at the end of the
303 incubation period also differed significantly between species ($F = 794.07$; $P < 0.0001$) (Fig.2c).
304 Across sites, the C:N ratios declined significantly with time for rosemary litter ($P < 0.0001$).
305 Pine litter C:N ratios were much more erratic, first increasing between the 0- and 8-month
306 collection dates, and then declining between the 8- and 20-month collection dates. However,
307 the litter C:N ratio at the 20-month collection date did not differ from the initial one
308 ($P = 0.575$).

309 *Soil input*

310 Litterbag ash content, an indicator of soil infiltration/deposition on litter according to
311 Throop and Archer (2007), was generally greater in the abandoned agricultural field than in
312 the open forest site for both litter types throughout the study period, and increased
313 significantly in the last stages of the decomposition experiment for both litter types (Fig. 5).
314 At the 20-month collection date, soil input into Aleppo pine litterbags was two-fold greater in
315 the abandoned agricultural field than that in the open forest site ($F = 43.82$; $P < 0.0001$), while
316 rosemary litterbags did not differ significantly in the ash percentage of retrieved litter between
317 the two sites ($F = 0.58$; $P = 0.46$).

318 *Factors controlling mass loss rates for each litter type*

319 Across sites, there was no relation between percentage mass loss, C or N content, and soil
320 temperature, water content or any of the rainfall parameters (event size, intensity or duration).
321 Interestingly, the ash content of the litter was strongly correlated with the total duration of

322 rainfall events for both pine ($r = 0.717$, $P < 0.01$) and rosemary ($r = 0.819$, $P < 0.01$) litter
323 throughout the study period. For rosemary, parameters related to litter quality (N content or
324 C:N) were found to explain between 33 and 37% of the variation in mass loss rates at the 14-
325 and 17-month sampling dates, respectively. For Aleppo pine, ash content explained 44% of
326 the variation in mass loss rates at both the 17- and 20-month sampling dates (Table 3).

327

328 **DISCUSSION**

329 The litter decay constants ($k = 0.14 - 0.57 \text{ yr}^{-1}$) and mass loss percentages (20- 55%) after
330 20 months observed in this study are similar to those reported for short-term decomposition
331 studies in other Mediterranean ecosystems (Castro et al. 2010; García-Pausas et al. 2004;
332 Grünzweig et al. 2007; Rodríguez-Pleguezuelo et al. 2009; Rovira and Vallejo 2002). The
333 lack of correlation between mass loss rates and soil temperature, water availability or any of
334 the precipitation parameters was somewhat expected, and is in agreement with the findings of
335 several studies in other water-limited ecosystems (Kemp et al. 2003; Steinberger 1990;
336 Vanderbilt et al. 2008; Whitford et al. 1986), suggesting that other physicochemical processes
337 may strongly influence the decomposition dynamics in these ecosystems.

338 The single exponential decay model adequately described the short-term decomposition
339 dynamics for both Aleppo pine and rosemary litter. However, different decomposition
340 patterns were found between species. The fact that rosemary litter decomposed about three
341 times faster than Aleppo pine litter across sites highlights the importance of litter chemical
342 composition in short-term decomposition processes in this water-limited ecosystem. In
343 addition to lower initial concentrations of most macro- and micro-nutrients in pine litter than
344 in rosemary litter (Table 2), low decomposition rates of Aleppo pine litter may further reflect
345 the high concentrations of lignin, suberin, resins, fats and waxes (Boddi et al. 2002;
346 Coûteaux et al. 2002), which are highly resistant to biodegradation (Minderman 1968).
347 Despite the fact that similar initial C and N percentages were shown between litter types,
348 previous studies have reported higher lignin concentrations in *Pinus halepensis* litter (31-

349 36%) than in *Rosmarinus officinalis* litter (24%) (Kaloustian et al. 2000; Rovira and Vallejo
350 2002). Although both litter types may have been colonized by soil microorganisms few days
351 or weeks after deployment, microbial biomass invading Aleppo pine litter may have been
352 predominantly limited by carbon quality, as it has been found in other ecosystems (Hobbie
353 2000; Manzoni et al. 2010). This could explain the fact that rosemary litter decomposed faster
354 than pine litter, showing net N immobilization in the early stages of decomposition, in
355 contrast to the net N release exhibited by pine litter (Fig. 2a; b).

356 Rosemary litter appears to be more easily decomposable by microorganisms than Aleppo
357 pine litter in this Mediterranean ecosystem. In addition to the net immobilization of
358 exogenous N by soil microorganisms exhibited in the early stages of decomposition,
359 parameters related to litter quality (N content or C:N) were found to explain the variations in
360 mass loss in the last stages of decomposition. The higher decay rates observed for rosemary
361 litter in the open forest than in the abandoned agricultural field site were consistent with the
362 higher soil microbial biomass and respiration rates (Table 1b; Almagro et al. 2009) previously
363 observed in the former than in the latter, suggesting that there may be greater decomposer
364 activity in the open forest than in the abandoned agricultural field site. This assumption is
365 supported by the fact that both species exhibited higher peaks of net N immobilization (a
366 good indicator of microbial activity in litter decomposition studies; Aerts et al. 2006; Hobbie
367 2000) in the open forest than in the abandoned agricultural field site (Fig.2b). Net N
368 immobilization occurs when a new external input of N (e.g., fresh litterfall) becomes
369 accessible to microorganisms and is incorporated into the microbial biomass (Berg 1988; Frey
370 et al. 2000). Despite differences in N patterns during the decomposition process between litter
371 types, net N immobilization peaked at the 17-month collection date for both species, shortly
372 after the time of maximum litterfall occurrence (mid-summer) in this Mediterranean
373 ecosystem (personal observation). Besides the higher soil microbial biomass found in the
374 open forest in comparison to the abandoned agricultural field site, microbial decomposers in

375 the open forest presumably have greater access to exogenous N due to higher soil mineral N
376 and greater litterfall inputs in the open forest (Tables 1a; 1b).

377 Conversely, mass loss rates for Aleppo pine litter were about two times higher in the
378 abandoned agricultural field site than those in the open forest site, in spite of higher microbial
379 biomass in the latter than in the former. Aleppo pine needles, which have been identified as
380 the most recalcitrant litter type in Mediterranean ecosystems (Berg et al. 2010; Rovira and
381 Vallejo 2002), resist microbial breakdown and thereby decomposition dynamics may be
382 strongly dependent on abiotic processes. First, the higher aboveground biomass of Aleppo
383 pine patches in the open forest in comparison to the abandoned agricultural field site may
384 have blocked a greater fraction of the total incoming solar radiation to the soil surface, thus
385 decreasing decomposition by photodegradation (Austin and Vivanco 2006; Dirks et al. 2010;
386 Henry et al. 2008; Parton et al. 2007). Greater aboveground biomass in the open forest may
387 have also led to increased interception of rainfall, thus decreasing physical fragmentation of
388 litter by raindrop impact and splash (Whitford 2002). Second, the presence of a thick litter
389 layer at the soil surface beneath Aleppo pine canopies in the open forest site may have
390 prevented lateral transport of soil particles (Bochet et al. 2006), thus avoiding physical
391 fragmentation of litter by abrasion (Throop and Archer 2007, 2009). Conversely, the more
392 open canopy of Aleppo pine patches in the abandoned agricultural field site, which lacked a
393 litter layer on the soil surface, resulted in higher rates of soil loss and runoff (Martínez-Mena
394 et al. 2008) and, as a consequence, a two-fold higher soil input into pine litterbags was
395 observed at this site (Fig. 5). Interestingly, significantly higher mass loss rates of Aleppo pine
396 litter in the abandoned agricultural field site than in the open forest site were only observed in
397 the last stages of the decomposition experiment, when most high-intensity rainfall events and
398 associated erosion processes occurred in the experimental area (Martínez-Mena et al. 2011).
399 In fact, the ash content was the parameter most tightly related to mass loss rates beneath
400 Aleppo pine canopies across sites at both the 17- and 20- month collection dates (Table 3),
401 suggesting that soil water erosion may have contributed to enhance litter decay during the

402 later stages of the decomposition experiment. Soil detachment and transport processes may
403 cause fragmentation or abrasion of litter (Throop and Archer 2007), thus increasing the
404 surface area available for solar radiation exposure, which has been found to accelerate
405 decomposition of lignin (Austin and Ballaré 2010). Also, soil deposition may facilitate
406 microbial litter colonization (Hamer et al. 2009; Throop and Archer 2009), and once the
407 lignin has been degraded mainly by sunlight, the labile compounds encapsulated in the lignin
408 linkages become more susceptible to microbial attack (Austin and Ballaré 2010; Foereid et al.
409 2010; Henry et al. 2008).

410

411 In conclusion, the results of this study suggest that short-term decomposition drivers may
412 differ depending on litter type in this Mediterranean ecosystem. Decomposition patterns of
413 the more labile rosemary litter were related to microbial activity, whereas decomposition of
414 the more recalcitrant pine litter was driven mainly by abiotic factors. The incorporation of soil
415 erosion as an important driver of litter decomposition would be a significant step towards the
416 development of mechanistic models of litter decomposition in Mediterranean ecosystems,
417 where changes in vegetation structure and increases in soil erosion rates are expected as a
418 result of future climate change. However, site-specific manipulative experiments explicitly
419 addressing the net effect of soil erosion on aboveground litter decomposition dynamics in
420 these dry ecosystems are necessary before we can fully understand the relative importance of
421 soil erosion with respect to other potential controlling factors such as litter quality parameters.

422

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433

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Table 1a. Main characteristics of the experimental area. Numerical values are means (\pm standard errors).

	Open forest		Abandoned agricultural field	
	<i>R. officinalis</i>	<i>P. halepensis</i>	<i>R. officinalis</i>	<i>P. halepensis</i>
<i>Site characteristics</i>				
Species richness	10		8	
Plant cover (%)	42	16	15	11
Relative abundance (%)	64	24	42	31
Standing biomass (g m^{-2})*	6862 \pm 4318 ^a (n= 16)		735 \pm 103 ^b (n= 8)	
Stem density (stems m^{-2})*	2.76 \pm 0.57 ^a (n= 16)		1.9 \pm 0.57 ^b (n= 8)	
Mean tree stem diameter (cm)*	8.37 \pm 0.4 ^a (n= 30)		3.97 \pm 0.48 ^b (n= 21)	
Mean shrub stem diameter (cm)*	1.72 \pm 0.07 ^a (n= 993)		1.86 \pm 0.09 ^a (n= 510)	
Plant cover (%)*	65 \pm 3.9 ^a (n= 31)		35 \pm 3.5 ^b (n= 28)	
Aboveground litterfall ($\text{g m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$)*	267.5 \pm 17.85 ^a (n=10)		184.1 \pm 17.8 ^b (n=10)	

* Within each row, different lowercase superscript letters (a-b) indicate statistically significant differences between land uses/sites ($P < 0.05$), according to Tukey's test. For more details on soil or site characteristics, see both Martínez-Mena et al. (2008) and Almagro et al. (2009).

Table 1b. Soil characteristics for each microsite (cover type) within each land-use. Numerical values are means (\pm standard errors).

Factors	Soil characteristics						
	SOC (g kg ⁻¹)	Soil N (g kg ⁻¹)	C:N	Soil microbial biomass (mg kg ⁻¹)			
Aleppo pine patches							
Open forest	41.28 \pm 3.66 ^a (n=8)	2.41 \pm 0.17 ^a (n=8)	17.25 ^a (n=8)	1052.42 \pm 131.5 ^a (n=8)			
Abandoned field	19.43 \pm 3.64 ^b (n=8)	1.58 \pm 0.12 ^b (n=8)	11.81 ^b (n=8)	747.46 \pm 83.5 ^b (n=8)			
Rosemary patches							
Open forest	20.88 \pm 1.66 ^a (n=8)	1.70 \pm 0.16 ^a (n=8)	13.11 ^a (n=8)	558.0 \pm 71.4 ^a (n=8)			
Abandoned field	14.73 \pm 1.56 ^b (n=8)	1.28 \pm 0.13 ^b (n=8)	11.53 ^a (n=8)	468.82 \pm 48.33 ^a (n=8)			
ANOVA	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>	
Land-use	14.13	0.001	19.72	< 0.0001	4.32	0.047	4.82
Microsite (cover type)	11.34	0.002	13.13	< 0.0001	1.71	0.201	18.56
Land-use x microsite	4.44	0.044	2.20	0.149	1.31	0.262	1.44

Notes: Soil properties were analyzed with a two-way ANOVA, in which land use and microsite (cover type) were considered the main effects. Within microsites, means with different lowercase superscript letters (a-b) differ significantly between land-uses/sites ($P < 0.05$). Bold values indicate significant effects ($P < 0.05$)

Table 2. Initial characteristics of the leaf litter material used in the decomposition experiment. For each litter type, means \pm standard errors (n=3 replicates of each litter) are reported. The units of the litter characteristics are given in mg g⁻¹.

Litter characteristics	<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>
Water content	44.60 \pm 12.8 ^a	38.80 \pm 12.8 ^a
Ash content	81.0 \pm 24 ^a	112.0 \pm 17 ^a
C	470 \pm 42 ^a	466.5 \pm 0.38 ^a
N	9.8 \pm 0.8 ^a	10 \pm 0.8 ^a
C:N	47.56 \pm 3.48 ^a	47.47 \pm 4.08 ^a
Ca	15.8 \pm 0.3 ^a	17.2 \pm 0.3 ^b
K	1.32 \pm 0.08 ^a	7.13 \pm 0.01 ^b
Mg	1.61 \pm 0.02 ^a	2.07 \pm 0.01 ^b
Na	0.90 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.99 \pm 0.00 ^b
S	0.56 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.98 \pm 0.00 ^b
P	0.01 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.01 \pm 0.00 ^b
Cu	0.01 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.01 \pm 0.00 ^a
Fe	0.48 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.57 \pm 0.01 ^b
Mn	0.02 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.02 \pm 0.00 ^b
Zn	0.03 \pm 0.00 ^a	0.20 \pm 0.00 ^b

Notes: Different letters (a-b) within the same row indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between litter types, according to Tukey's test.

Table 3. Relationship between the percentage of ash-free dry mass remaining and potential decomposition controls at each of the six collection dates.

Time (month)	<i>Pinus halepensis</i>					<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>						
	variable	R ²	β_0	β_1	F	P	variable	R ²	β_0	β_1	F	P
4	No model						No model					
8	N (%)	0.34	-0.252	-0.211	5.69	0.044	No model					
11	No model						No model					
14	No model						N (%)	0.33	-0.43	-0.81	6.46	0.029
17	Ash (%)	0.44	0.067	-0.138	9.65	0.011	C:N ratio	0.37	-3.77	0.97	6.92	0.029
20	Ash (%)	0.44	0.283	-0.251	9.78	0.011	No model					

Note: Data were natural-log transformed. Linear regressions were calculated for each collection date (including data for both sites); only statistically significant regression parameters are shown.

Fig.1. Rainfall events (a), topsoil temperature (0-3 cm) (b), and water content (0-10 cm) (c) for each land use/site throughout the study period. Due to technical difficulties, no data are available from 3rd September to 20th December 2007 and from 16th March to 10th June 2008 for the forest site.

Fig.2. Mean mass remaining (a), changes in N content (b) and C:N ratios (c) with time for different litter types in different land uses/sites. For each litter type, significant differences in mass remaining, changes in N content and C:N ratios between land uses/sites are denoted by different lowercase letters (a-b) ($P < 0.05$), according to Tukey's test.

Fig.3. Average decomposition constants (k ; Eq.1) and standard errors (SE) for Aleppo pine and rosemary leaf litter in the two land uses/sites. Within each species, values with different lowercase superscript letter differ significantly between sites ($P > 0.05$). Within sites, means with different uppercase superscript letter differ significantly between species ($P < 0.05$).

Fig.4. Relationships between remaining mass and remaining C (a) and N (b) for Aleppo pine and rosemary litter across sites. For both species, C losses closely tracked mass loss patterns. However, there was a net loss of the total N mass with time for rosemary litter across sites ($y = 51.66 + 0.47x$, $R^2=0.20$), but no relationship was found between total mass loss and N loss for pine litter.

Fig.5. Mean \pm standard error (SE) for percentage ash in retrieved litter across land uses/sites. Within each species and sampling period, values with different lowercase letters differ significantly between land uses/sites. Different uppercase letters at both sides of the vertical dashed line indicate significant differences in ash content between sampling periods ($P < 0.05$). For both species, ash content in the 17- and 20-month collection period was significantly higher than that in previous sampling periods ($P < 0.05$).

Averages for soil-free leaves are $8.10\% \pm 2.4\%$ ash and $11.28\% \pm 1.71\%$ ash (mean \pm SE) for Aleppo pine and rosemary, respectively.

